

References

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Chemical Constituents of *Polycarpone loeflingiae*†

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POLYCARPONE *loeflingiae* edgew HKf, syn. *P. prostratum*, belonging to family Caryophyllaceae is found throughout the hotter part of India in fields and waste lands. It is also distributed in tropical Asia and Africa¹. There appears to be no work carried out on the genus *Polycarpone* in general and on *P. loeflingiae* in particular. This is the first report on the chemical constituents of *P. loeflingiae*. Under our programme of screening Indian plants for a wide range of biological activity, 50% alcoholic extract of the whole plant (aerial parts only) of *P. loeflingiae* showed good spasmolytic activity² (75% inhibition of BaCl₂ induced spasm at 50 µg ml⁻¹ concentration) and was taken up for detailed chemical investigation.

The plant material (aerial parts only) was collected from Chilapata, Jalpaiguri, West Bengal, India in March 1982 by the Botany Division of C.D.R.I. (Lucknow) and a voucher specimen of the same is preserved in the herbarium of the Institute.

The shed-dried whole plant (3 kg dry weight) was powdered and extracted with 90% ethanol at room temperature by percolation method. The total alcoholic extract concentrate was successively fractionated with hexane and chloroform. The resulting residue was taken up in methanol and filtered to remove the inorganic salts. The three well defined fractions, hexane soluble, chloroform soluble and methanol soluble thus obtained were chromatographed separately over silica gel column to yield the following compounds.

The hexane soluble fraction on chromatography yielded hentriacontane (i), m.p. 68°; hentriacontanol (ii), m.p. 84–6°; β-amyrene (iii), m.p. 206–10°, its acetate, m.p. 20–82°; and a sterol mixture (iv) resolved into β-sitosterol and stigmasterol on chromatography of their acetates on AgNO₃ impregnated silica gel plates.

The chloroform soluble fraction yielded additional quantities of β-amyrene (iii) and the sterol mixture (iv), alongwith two tetrahydroxytriterpenes: (v), m.p. 285–87° (vi), m.p. 256–60°; and β-D-glucoside of β-sitosterol (vii), m.p. 280–85°. The identity of (v) was confirmed as saikogenin-A (3β, 16β, 23, 28-tetrahydroxyolean-11,13-diene) by comparing its ir, uv, nmr and ms with those reported literature³, and preparation of diacetyl derivative, m.p. 200–01° (lit.³ 201–04°). While (vi) was found to be its 16α-hydroxy-isomer, saikogenin-D (3β, 16α, 23, 28-tetrahydroxyolean-11,13-diene)³.

The methanol soluble fraction of the alcoholic extract on chromatography yielded a pure saponin, carponoside-A (viii), m.p., 172–74°. On acid hydrolysis (10% methanolic sulphuric acid) carponoside-A yielded the genin C₃₀H₄₈O₄, m.p. 256–60°, [α]_D²⁵ -42° (c, 1.0 EtOH); λ_{max} 240, 250 and 262 nm; and was identified as saikogenin-D (3β, 16α, 23, 28-tetrahydroxyolean-11,13(18)-diene) and the sugars were identified as glucose and arabinose by pc from the aqueous hydrolysate. Thus, carponoside-A is a new saponin different from saikosaponins of diene type reported^{4,5} so far. The presence of these triterpenoids both in the free state as well as saponins (carponoside-A) in *P. loeflingiae* (Caryophyllaceae) are of taxonomic interest since these triterpenoids were first isolated⁶ as artifacts of saikosaponins-A and -D from *Bupleurum falatum* belonging to Umbelliferae. The existence of these saponins with olean-11,13(18)-diene system were later reported in other species *Bupleurum rotundifolium*⁵. None of the above reported compounds showed spasmolytic activity.

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